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SYSTEM OF MANAGING EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE – AN EMERGING SCENARIO AND FUTURE TRENDS.

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Abstract

Managing employees' performance is a continuous process. It involves making sure that the performance of employees contributes to the goals of their teams and the business as a whole. The aim is to continuously improve the performance of individuals and that of the organisation. The undisputable transition from production-based to knowledge-based economy has resulted in to the rapid rise of knowledge-based organizations across nations. Knowledge workers have become primary creators of wealth and jobs. It is common that organisation in present scenario needs a community of high performing individuals and teams to go beyond what is simply required to achieve extraordinary results. Any system in an organisation change as it has at its base objective of organisational improvement. And the same goes with performance management system. The arrival of the Internet and rapid accessibility of information triggered the current change at the peak speed. Exponential growth in mobile devices and remote working has further strengthened this social shift. Some companies are already achieving better results by re-focusing performance management on strengths. For that the organisation needs to cultivate a culture of commitment to a workplace that is trusting, inclusive, creative, and respectful which is always been a result of good performance managing machinery.

This paper focuses on the changing system of managing performance in present day organisation and also focuses on the future changing scenario.

Key words: Performance Management system, performance reviews, feedback, Assessments, approaches, rewards.

INTRODUCTION:

The concept of performance management became known in early 1980 when total quality management became necessary for quality performance. The process of performance Management is the process which is carried out throughout the year. In today's competitive global business environment the contribution of each employee counts in the progress of the organisation. The main objective of performance management system is to achieve the capacity of the employees to the full potential in favour of both the employee and the organization, by defining the expectations in terms of roles, responsibilities and accountabilities, required competencies and the expected behaviours. It is a continuous and on-going proactive mechanism to manage the performance of an employee and achieves the set targets on a real-time basis. Organizations are run and steered by people. It is through people that goals are set and objectives are realized. Eccles and Pyburn (1992,) argue that financial performance measures are 'lagging indicators' since they determine the outcomes of

management's actions after a time period. Therefore, it is difficult to establish a relationship between managers' actions and the reported financial results. Also, any corrective action has nothing to do with the past and it will be difficult to identify which action leads to a particular result. In addition, financial performance measures give little or no guidance to future performance since they do not include any measures relating to customers' satisfaction and organizational learning. Furthermore, Eccles and Pyburn (1992) claim that financial performance measures are oriented internally rather than externally. The performance of an organization is thus dependent upon the sum total of performance of its members. (Smith, 2002). Management accounting literature also advocates the use of non-financial performance measures as a tool in order to overcome the deficiencies attributed to financial measures. The success of an organization will therefore depend on its ability to measure accurately the performance of its members and use it objectively to optimize them as a vital resource (Biswajeet 2009). In the present highly competitive environment, organizations have to ensure peak performance of their employees continuously in order to compete and survive at the market place effectively (Prasad 2005). Performance management is the current buzzword and is the need in the current times of cut throat competition and then organizational battle for leadership. Thus, the performance management process starts with the joining of a new incumbent in a system and ends when the employee quits the organization. As organizations develop and refine their performance management systems, they get better, and in time, excellent. In the early stages, before successive cycles help to mature the system, an organization may use its components as reactive, or even defensive, accountability tools. As the system matures, however, the components will be used proactively, as tools to improve future performance.

REASONS FOR THE NEED TO CHANGE:

1. Became a tool to achieve collective goal:

In past the managers used performance management tool as some requirement by the HR department i.e. the line managers always thought that it is required by the HR department as an input for Pay raises, Succession Planning or for devising a training programme etc. and this fell in the list of routine activities. Now it has in its real sense become a tool to achieve group performance and thereby group goals. Now new easy run softwares are available or devised to make its implementation part easy. Such softwares have made it possible to cascade the goals and operational objective in such a manner that every employee in the organisation knows their part of goal to be achieved which was to a certain extent not possible manually. Again, keeping track of hundreds or thousands of Development plans was near impossible with manual systems. This resulted in fragmented development of individuals and fragmented development plans that did not necessarily address competency gaps. Similarly it also enables the managers to keep a continuous keep track on achieved part of the employees' goal as a routine exercise.

2. Shift from regular performance review session to shorter touch-base meetings:

The regular performance review session replaced with higher frequency shorter touch-base meetings. The One on One process provides a mechanism where both managers and employees are able to make relevant notes on performance related issues (such as progress on their goals and Objectives) throughout the year. When the annual appraisal is conducted at the end of the performance period, both parties are better prepared and have a full record of achievement This feature also promotes an ongoing dialogue between managers and employees to ensure that both are on track to achieve their goals for the year.

3. Need to reduce administrative work load:

Managing employee performance always had the bearing on increasing administrative work loads which again became a big task for large organisations. These systems also required HR department to make duplicate data entries for all additions, changes and deletions to staff because entries had to be made in both the payroll system and the Performance Management system. Therefore a system had to be devised so that all changes made to payroll are automatically made to the Performance Management application and thereby reduce the administrative work loads.

4. Need to align outside the traditional vertical hierarchy:

As the organisation grows, and lends up into developing a large structure, there also arise for employees and managers, a need to align outside of their traditional vertical hierarchy ensures both people are aligned to achieve a common goal that supports a higher level strategy. These new alignment techniques are referred to as horizontal or dog leg alignment.

5. Need for establishing a link between Performance Management and retention:

The undisputable transition from production-based to knowledge-based economy has resulted in to the rapid rise of knowledge-based organizations across nations. Such organizations are people focused and knowledge has since become a nation's most important resource, while knowledge workers have become primary creators of wealth and jobs. Retaining them is becoming a huge task. Employees hate ambiguity and desire clear direction so they can complete the work that is required of them. Performance Management addresses this need, particularly if the manager is conducting high frequency One on One meetings resulting into establishment of link between Performance retention and employee retention.

6. Need for establishing a link between Performance Management Succession and Talent Planning:

Performance Management system helps in implementation of talent management Potential staff who are then put through accelerated learning and development programs proves to be an asset of the organisation. Identifying employees who have particular experience, qualifications, and who are having high potential and ability to work can be recognised easily.

7. Justification to Pay raises and salary:

The organisation can provide proper justification for salary and pay raises. By implementing an effective Performance Management system, organizations can rank employees according to how well they achieved their business and development objectives. Pay raises now gain objectivity and are directed mainly towards those employees who are truly the top achievers. The information generated through the Performance Management system provides for the justification for all salary and pay raises in an organisation

CHANGING SCENARIO:

1. Single business model:

With a single business model catering for all phases of the performance management cycle, it is straightforward to construct reports that draw on information from across the business. In this way, users can find information at their fingertips for decision making and resolve anomalies. It creates a Unified environment. Such unified environment also lends itself to collaboration in a way that modular performance management suites find difficult to emulate. With a single business model it is feasible to allow all of those involved in a process to share access (subject to security permissions) to the same data and to assign them to the same workflow, as appropriate. In this way the unified model overcomes undesirable functional boundaries that are reinforced by traditional performance management design.

2. Computer based Performance Monitoring CBPM:

Computer based Performance Monitoring CBPM is the process of observing ongoing employee actions using computers or other non-human methods. The number of employees monitored through CBPM has increased drastically in the past 20 years. In the early 1990s, about one third of employees in the US were being monitored Computer based. By 2001, approximately 78% were monitored Computer based, and in 2013 that number more than likely increased even more. The reason for this steep increase is that CBPM apparently is an effective means of increasing productivity. The biggest advantage of CBPM seems to be that it provides information for concrete results-based performance evaluations. There is an obvious relation between more employee monitoring and controlling stress levels in the workforce. In some cases individual employees who are over stressed, leave the organization. If these individuals are more productive workers, and especially if they are knowledge workers, it has huge impact on organizational productivity.

3. Competency-Based Performance Management:

The performance appraisal process evaluates specific employee skills and the employee's success in using those skills to produce products or services for the organization. Competency-based performance appraisal, on the other hand, evaluates large sets of capabilities and knowledge which, if put to good use, can significantly improve organizational productivity to a much greater extent than just doing a job using an existing skill set. Because jobs have been changing at a rapid pace over the past 20 years, competency based performance management is becoming a more useful form for performance appraisal than the historical skill-based, transactional process. The nature of work is changing from single-skilled jobs to multi-skilled jobs, from repetitive tasks to problem solving tasks, from individual work to teamwork, and from functional specialization to collaboration. Taking a look at the ways in which work is changing, we can understand why it may be necessary for the organization to move from skill-based performance appraisal to evaluations based on larger-scale competencies. Because competencies are becoming so significant in organizations, the performance management systems need to be redesigned so that it evaluates the skills and capabilities that are most important to the business. Innovative software helps here. Using powerful web-based platforms provides a completely unified, scalable and auditable computing environment that can be built and maintained by end-user departments.

4. Minimizing the rater's inconsistency:

One method is to gather all of the raters, within a given division, department, or section of the organization, in one place where they discuss each of the individuals being evaluated. A process called "calibration" provides the organization with a methodology for normalization of grades across raters. Many organizations have done something similar to the process of calibration for years by gathering groups of managers together and, through a series of discussions, coming to an agreement on the rating of each of their employees. Calibration is done face-to-face with a group of managers who are responsible for one division or department within the organization. However, the end result of the calibration process is not necessarily a ranking of employees. It is designed simply to standardize, or even out, evaluations between multiple managers.

5. Linking reviews to organizational goals:

Linking of performance reviews with organisational goals is becoming a common feature nowadays. Companies which are linking reviews with organisational goals automatically establish attainable goals. It makes them feel like an important part of the whole. When employees are involved in crafting organizational goals, they are far more likely to understand them, buy into them, and work toward them. When leaders bring up these goals again and again in performance reviews, it reinforces employee efforts.

6. Making of review criteria as objective as possible:

One of the major criticisms levelled at performance reviews is that they are based on subjective criteria. The subjective criteria can only give the perception of the appraiser which is always a qualitative in nature. Presently companies opt for performance reviews to be in hard numbers. For eg. how many calls are actually being made and how much return business they are generating. When one keep an eye on these follow-up calls all year long, one can more accurately track and make review accordingly.

7. Performance reviews no longer a confrontation session:

Performance reviews sessions are no longer a confrontation sessions rather are conversation sessions to discuss progress of an employee toward goals and to put specific actions in place to achieve those goals. Such sessions are now focused on coaching aspect for all levels of employees. The words 'performance review' no longer call up an image of a king pronouncing a sentence on the nervous employee, but like a best leaders draw employees out, solicit their ideas for improvement, and offer concrete suggestions on how to better pursue the goals that are set together.

8. Employees shifted from being passive recipients to active agents:

Employee expectations have changed. The present generation employee expects more. More involvement, more accountability, and more transparency. When it comes to managing their performance, employees have shifted from being passive recipients to active agents. Not satisfied with

a one-way download of performance feedback, employees want to participate in the performance data collection process.. Managers have changed too. Command and control is no longer a useful tool but managers are expected to guide and coach, provide balanced constructive feedback and inspire, rather than enforce, performance.

9. Developmental interview:

More focus is nowadays on developmental interviews. It is well known that employees need to know exactly what they must do to improve and increase the rating on the next review, and follow-up feedback on progress is essential for changing behaviour. The developmental interview focuses on areas for improvement over time. Managers in present scenario motivate employees come up with their own objectives and strategies for improvement. This is possible with the help of developmental interview.

10. Feedback in real time:

Instead of traditional performance reviews, nowadays most of the employees prefer to receive feedback in real time; more frequent and instant reviews that may even be delivered on their mobile devices. Employees are used to getting feedback and awards just for participating and they are not willing to toil for years without recognition or a promotion. Employees like to check in often to receive encouragement and tips on how to improve their performance, and they like to be rewarded for their innovation. Employees with less than 5 years experience are eager to learn and develop, and they are flexible to change when provided with clear and specific feedback in honest dialogues.

MANAGING PERFORMANCE IN FUTURE:

HR managers will be responsible for keeping all staff continuously up-to-date on goals, strategies and priorities through mobile, network, fixed multi-media and other devices. In future Performance Management technology will be the tool that is used hour-by-hour by all staff to help get the right things done. Each individual will have a continuously evolving performance plan comprising what they have committed to achieve, how they need to go about achieving it and the growth they need to achieve.

Leaders will be responsible for ensuring individual optimal performance by identifying factors that inhibit personal motivation and taking steps to fix them. Leaders and managers will be able to monitor performance plans and intervene on a case by- case basis when necessary. Assessments will be continuously added to, and updated, by any interested party to any element of any performance plan. Formal evaluations or appraisals will be snapshots of the prevailing data. Technology will provide feedback and guidance to all users on how to optimise data quality, process compliance and individual performance and development.

Current employee performance management approaches is slowly becoming obsolete. It gives in reality little importance to the ways employees work, and give and receive information. A new method that involves colleagues, incorporates social media and focuses on real-time, year-round feedback can revitalize the process, and connect employee performance more directly to business goals and results.

The future performance management process needs to eliminate the heavy administrative workloads on HR department during midyear and year-end reviews, and should focus instead on real-time feedback — employing easy-to-use, social-media-inspired software etc. The most important task here is to remove traditional Forced Ranking system Today, rather than being pushed into a force ranking system, the employees should receive a combination of feedback, coaching and development advice that motivates collaborative behaviour.

There also arise a need for bringing change in feedback process and learning environment. A new online feedback system should be developed that can allow employees to give and receive feedback rapidly and easily at any time. Employees could give colleagues a thumbs-up or thumbs-down rating. A thumbs down rating triggers a need to focus on the loopholes in the system as well as will help to

focus on bridging the skill required. As well as the thumbs up will acknowledge that the employee is moving on the right path and will also serve as a tool for motivation.

The performance report will be linked with flexible rewards and not just fixed rewards. This will enable the employee to opt for a choice in rewards than the traditional fixed rewards. For example, a younger employee with consistently good reviews from superiors, colleagues and subordinates might opt to use his points for greater current cash compensation or an opportunity for company-paid education, while an older employee might choose rewards with an eye toward maximizing retirement income.

CONCLUSION:

It is a known fact that since few decades, Performance management system has become a process and a tool contributing towards the effective management of individuals and teams with the goal of achieving higher levels of organizational performance. Performance management solutions have been in existence for many years, and in the past 10 years we've seen their adoption and feature set grow. This momentum will likely continue for several years. Performance management started with a focus on consolidating information from multiple general ledgers and then moved on to providing a real system alternative to spread sheet budgeting. Leaders use performance management strategically to define outcomes and to establish an integrated, shared understanding within their organization about what is meant to be achieved, and how. It is also a way to measure results and to check that the organization has the skills and capacity to achieve its outcomes. Any system in an organisation change as it has at its base objective of organisational improvement. And the same goes with performance management system. The arrival of the Internet and rapid accessibility of information triggered the current change at the peak speed. Exponential growth in mobile devices and remote working has further strengthened this social shift. Some companies are already achieving better results by re-focusing performance management on strengths. By focusing on strengths and key skills required for future success, organisations can create a more engaging, constructive and positive performance management system to better support their employees and business strategy.

References:

1. Akinyele S. T., *Educational Research* 1(8) (2010)
2. Akua Asantewaa Aforo¹, Kodjo Asafo-Adjei Antwi, *Journal of Business Management and Economics* 3(8) (2012)
3. Bhattacharya Dipak Kumar, "Performance management system and strategies", *Pearson education*, 2011, pp. 13-17.
4. Bhattacharjee Sharmistha, Santoshi Sengupta, *VSRD-IJBMR* 1(8) (2011) 496-513.
5. Clinton Wingrove; *Performance Management 2020*; Business Today 4-2012
6. Eccles, R. and Pyburn, P.J., (1992) Creating a comprehensive system to measure performance, *Management accounting (UK)*, Vol. 74, No. 4, October, 41-44.
7. Evans, H. et al (1996) Who needs performance management? *Management Accounting Dec.*, 20-25.
8. George Ndemo Ochoti, Elijah Maronga, Stephen Muathe, Robert Nyamao Nyabwanga, Peter Kibet Ronoh, *International Journal of Business and Social Science* 3(20) (2012) 37-46.
9. Jawaria Andleeb Qureshi, Asad Shahjehan, Zia-ur-Rehman, Bilal Afsar, *African Journal of Business Management* 4(9) (2010) 1856-1862.
10. Lyle Potgieter *Performance Management CEO People Streme From Performance Appraisal to Performance Management*
11. Mohammad Tanvi Newaz, *International Journal of Business and Management Tomorrow* 2(3) (2012) 1-10.
12. Pattanayak B., *Human Resource Management* (PHI Learning Pvt. Ltd, 2009).
13. Prasad L.M., *Human Resource Management* (Sultan Chand & Sons: Educational Publishers, 2006).
14. Rao T. V., (2011) "Performance management and appraisal system sage publication India pvt. Ltd.

15. Smith M.J. (2002), Gaming Non Financial Performance Measures, *Journal of Management Accounting Research*, Vol. 14.
16. Toppo Leena, Twinkle Prusty, *IOSR Journal of Business and Management* 3(5) (2012) 01-06.